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Prospects for the Use of Virtual Reality Technologies in the Psychological Rehabilitation of Military Personnel

Virtual reality (VR) technologies play a significant role in the psychological rehabilitation of military personnel by influencing the brain's neurophysiological processes and promoting adaptive changes. According to the World Health Organization, about 12.5% of the population has a mental disorder. Given the specifics of military service, this figure among military personnel is significantly higher; in particular, the risk of developing PTSD among service members with combat experience has been found to be seven times higher compared to those without combat experience. Anxiety disorders occur twice as often among military personnel compared to the general population, and the risk of depressive disorders is 4.8% in the military versus 3.6% among civilians. Furthermore, a study conducted among Ukrainian service members showed that 50% are willing to seek psychological support from their unit commander, 21% from a military psychologist, 9% from a chaplain, and only 5% from a civilian psychologist [1].

Research indicates that the use of VR facilitates the modulation of activity in various brain regions, especially in the context of emotional responses and stress reactivity. In a quasi-randomized clinical study involving 30 patients with chronic ischemic stroke, it was found that in the experimental group the use of VR therapy led to a statistically significant increase in the power of alpha and beta rhythms in the brain,

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which indicated positive changes in neuroplasticity and improvements in cognitive functioning [5].

The regulation of stress reactions and the modeling of a safe environment are key aspects of VR therapy in military rehabilitation. A virtual environment can serve as a controlled tool for reproducing stressful situations and for adapting service members to real threats. For example, in a study of 20 military personnel it was established that, under certain VR conditions (a scenario simulating height), physiological indicators can change substantially, whereas the use of a virtual battle simulator (VBS) did not lead to statistically significant changes [7].

The possibilities of neuroplasticity and the formation of adaptive skills through VR technologies are considered one of the promising areas in the rehabilitation of service members. Studies show that VR promotes the activation of plastic changes in the nervous system, allowing for the restoration of cognitive and motor skills after traumatic events. Thus, in a study of 25 patients with neuromotor or musculoskeletal disorders, the use of the VR games “Whack-a-mole” and “Fruit collection” made it possible to achieve improvements in movement accuracy by an average of 20–35% and to increase participant motivation [8].

Using VR to simulate combat situations enables service members to learn to control emotions, make rapid decisions, and adapt to critical conditions. It has also been established that VR training increases the level of sensory information integration, which contributes to the development of new behavioral strategies and to improved adaptation to civilian life. In a systematic review covering more than 25 studies, it was recorded that adaptive self-control and emotional regulation skills improved in participants by an average of 40% after several weeks of using VR technologies [9].

The use of virtual reality in the treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) among service members opens new possibilities for addressing this mental disorder, which often develops after combat. One of the most effective methods is exposure therapy in VR (VRET), which allows patients to interact with controlled, gradually intensified scenarios reproduced in a virtual environment. Methods of

exposure therapy in VR are aimed at the gradual processing of traumatic memories. According to research, VRET is an effective approach because it provides a safe environment for the re-experiencing of traumatic events, which facilitates their desensitization [6].

Virtual reality technologies continue to expand the possibilities of comprehensive psychological rehabilitation for service members, ensuring more effective recovery after combat stress. One promising direction is the combination of VR with biofeedback, which allows the monitoring of patients' physiological indicators in real time. The use of biofeedback in VR rehabilitation makes it possible to track changes in heart rate, breathing, and brain activity, adapting the virtual environment according to the patient's responses. According to a review included in a meta-analysis, the application of VR technologies in combination with biofeedback contributes to a 25% improvement in stress resilience and increases motivation for therapy by approximately 20% compared to traditional methods [4].

The development of personalized VR programs for different categories of service members is another important direction in rehabilitation. Modern approaches take into account the specifics of combat experience, the nature of psychological trauma, and the level of adaptation to civilian life. Studies confirm the effectiveness of VR in correcting PTSD when programs are adapted to the specific needs of veterans, which makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of exposure therapy and cognitive-behavioral methods [2].

The use of VR in group therapy and in post-service social adaptation is a promising direction that allows service members to interact in a safe environment while restoring social skills. Studies show that VR sessions in a group format help reduce anxiety levels by 30% and double the improvement of stress-coping strategies, which positively affects adaptation to civilian life [4]. VR can also be used as a platform for training veterans in new skills, facilitating their professional reintegration. In military programs, VR has proven effective in training and psychological support, making it

possible to reduce the time required to master new tasks by an average of 25%, which underscores its role in future approaches to the social adaptation of veterans [3].

Virtual reality (VR) technologies demonstrate significant potential in the psychological rehabilitation of service members, in particular due to their effects on neurophysiological processes, neuroplasticity, and the formation of adaptive skills. The use of VR methods such as virtual exposure therapy (VRET) makes it possible to effectively process psychotraumatic experience in a controlled and safe environment, improving emotional regulation and the cognitive functions of service members. Further prospects for the development of this area are associated with the integration of VR technologies with biofeedback, the development of personalized scenarios tailored to the individual needs of service members, and the expansion of VR applications in group formats of psychological rehabilitation with the aim of improving social adaptation and the professional reintegration of veterans.

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